

Instructions for using the evaluation spreadsheet:

Copy and paste the turbine flows and spills from your original model solution into columns G and H, starting in row 4. The evaluation spreadsheet will check all constraints, and it will calculate the value of the generated power for all weeks and average it in cell R682. Total generated energy over the 13 simulated years is calculated in cell R685.

Instructions for using the “Frontline large scale GRG”, “Excel Sol. GRG with lin. const” and “Excel Solver Lin-QP”:

1. Ensure the Premium Analytic Solver from Frontline Systems is installed
2. Click on cell R682, click on Data/ Solver, build the model using the Excel solver procedures available from the Frontline Systems, and run the solver. An example setup of the objective function and constraints is displayed below:

Solver Parameters

Set Objective:

To: Max Min Value Of:

By Changing Variable Cells:

Subject to the Constraints:

-
-
-
-
-
-

Make Unconstrained Variables Non-Negative

Select a Solving Method:

Solving Method:
Simplex LP
Evolutionary

Select the GRG Nonlinear engine for Solver Problems that are smooth nonlinear. Select the LP Simplex engine for linear Solver Problems, and select the Evolutionary engine for Solver problems that are non-smooth.